

STRATEGIZING COMMUNICATION TO REMAIN RELEVANT; A MYTH OR A SAVIOR FOR MARKETERS IN TODAY'S COMPETITIVE WORLD

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ABSTRACT

Earlier, in the 20th century, Television was the most preferred channel for the Advertisers to promote their goods to the audience. Advertisers were following a particular set of strategy- the 30 second Television commercial, along with Press, Posters and Radio Advertising.

But now we can see that the Advertising scenario has completely changed. In today's world the choice of media for Advertisement has become a creative decision. Advertising is now, not just about producing magazines ads or radio and Television commercials – it's about communicating. Now we have many different and exciting ways of reaching a target market nationally as well as globally, we can see that brands are putting too much effort, and researches are going on for finding the new ways to connect with the target audience. The various different cultural aspects are being encountered by the advertisers to connect the audience now advertisers are even more precise about small differences in terms of region, religion, cast and customs. Non-verbal aspects of communication are also being touched like Chromatics, Chronemics and paralanguages are given importance while dealing with the different culture globally.

Paying attention in to culture in advertising is extremely important for brands that work on the global scales, especially if your brand is working in market that are culturally different to where they are based. Messages, Symbols, Rituals and even colors can have significantly different meanings and also the messages across the different cultural. Travelling across the cultural is simply about using the common sense and analyzing how the different elements of an advertising Campaign are impacted by cultural and modifying them to best speak to the target audience.

The new media has altered the trend of one way flow of information to interactive session, where the consumers have also become a part of the process. So instead of being force fed advertisement, users are now getting empowered to choose, diversified set of new options.

Key words: Advertising, Communication, Integrated marketing Communication, advertising campaigns and Media Usage

INTRODUCTION

Trends in the Advertising Industry

Advertising trends have evolved from the quintessentially traditional print ads and TV spots to new marketing strategies that include QR codes, co-branding, content marketing and online advertising. While print and TV are steadfast in the ad industry, new technology is opening new avenues to reach

consumers. For businesses that want to stay ahead of the curve with interactive advertising, these trends can do just the trick.

QR Codes

As the QR code or can say a “quick response” code it is a two-dimensional symbol in to the UPC (Universal Product Code, or "bar code") A QR code a digital action when scanned by a QR code reader as in the advertising, it has gained traction as an interactive tool in which consumers can scan the code to retrieve additional information about the product or promotion. When scanned by a smart phone, a QR code can initiate several actions, such as opening a website, making a phone call or sending an SMS message. Make a free QR code online using the QR Code Generator (see Resources) and place the symbol on your company’s business cards, brochures, coupons, print ads and even TV spots.

Co-Branding

Co-branding is a joint venture that combines the advertising efforts of two or more brands to create a new consumer product. Recent examples of co-branding include Isaac Mizrahi and Target, Crest Plus Scope, Ford F150 trucks and Harley Davidson motorcycles, and Apple and Nike. These brands have worked together to create new consumer products that elevate brand awareness while creating heightened consumer interest in newly launched products. Small businesses can take a cue from national brands by launching a co-branded ad campaign with another recognized, locally-owned company. For example, a car service center can partner with a detail shop to create mutual coupons for use at both businesses. This maximizes the use of advertising dollars while simultaneously creating a stronger promotion for the consumer.

Content Marketing

Content marketing is a term that began gaining popularity around 2003 with the birth of social media websites such as Facebook and Twitter. Content marketing includes advertorials (newspaper or magazine articles that are written editorially to promote your product), blogs or any other kind of content that is published on the web for promotional purposes. As a form of advertising, content marketing is effective at creating awareness when it comes to brand storytelling. Since the rise of social media, content marketing has strengthened connections between consumers and brands while creating a new advertising vehicle. Small businesses can capitalize on the power of content marketing by running advertorials or hosting a blog on their Web site.

✚ Online Advertising

Consumers use the web to find many things, including businesses and brands. When it comes to capitalizing on reaching consumers, advertisers are using tools such as Google AdWords to create online advertising campaigns. AdWords is a Google product that allows small businesses to create online advertisements with keyword and budget parameters to target their primary customers. Other trends in online advertising include marketing efforts such as search engine optimization (SEO -- the process of using keywords to get a website to rank higher in results as opposed to using AdWords); social media; mobile devices such as iPads and other handhelds; display ads; and website banner ads.

As we know that the Brands taking a stand when it comes to their values is nothing new. But putting their impact strategy at the forefront of their digital marketing strategy reflects a shift in how brands are framing themselves in response to global events.

And we're not just talking about reacting to disasters or socio-political events. Consumers want brands who take the initiative authentically and mindfully; who center themselves around the values and morals they stand.

Culture And Advertisement

Obviously advertising is a useful thing to the businesses that use it, and that's all of them if they expect to have any customers. It's a means of informing choice, and it's vital to new entrants in any market. When it comes to society however, and the big picture effects of advertising in general, it's not pretty. The report's conclusion is that advertising promotes values that are directly opposed to human wellbeing, environmental sustainability and a fair society. It ought to be considered a detrimental influence, and regulated accordingly.

That's not how advertisers see it of course. As far as they're concerned, they simply redistribute consumption, directing spending from this brand to that one. They promote choice, and simply reflect existing cultural values. In reality, advertising doesn't just expand market share, it expands the size of the market. "It seems," says the report, "that advertising may be encouraging society to save less, borrow more, work harder and consume greater quantities of material goods."

Advertising also impacts values. While it reflects society to a certain degree, it also has the effect of 'normalising' values or behaviour. With the average American exposed to between 500 and 1,000 commercial messages a day, it wields considerable power over what we consider normal. An example that came to mind for me was the idea of cosmetics for men. Only a few years ago, the idea that men might want to use moisturizers would have been laughable to most British men. A sustained advertising campaign from Nivea later, including prominent billboards at football stadiums, and there's nothing unusual at all about men using hand cream

- ✚ Culture affects everything, including advertising
- ✚ When advertising professionals don't take this seriously, things can go very wrong.
- ✚ We'll share a great example of a cultural blunder in advertising in just a little while, but first, it's important to understand the influences of culture in a little more detail.

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- ✚ When interacting within our native cultures, culture acts as a framework of shared understanding.
- ✚ However, when interacting with different cultures, this shared framework no longer applies, which results in cultural differences.

Culturally competent' people minimize the negative impact of cultural differences by re-establishing common frameworks for people from different cultures to interact within. In culturally-savvy international businesses, cultural insights are routinely applied across all business functions - whether HR, team building, foreign trade, negotiations or website design.

For obvious reasons, such cultural intelligence is critical to effective cross cultural advertising - particularly since materials are typically distributed within the public domain; risking company reputation. Since services and products are usually designed and marketed for a domestic audience, when the same product is then marketed at an international audience, the domestic advertising campaign will, in most cases, be ineffective.

Advertising Across Cultures

The essence of successful advertising is convincing people that a product is meant for them. By purchasing it, they will receive some benefit, whether lifestyle, status, convenience or financial.

However, when an advertising campaign is taken abroad, the target audience typically have different values and perceptions as to what enhances status or what constitutes convenience. As such, these differences make the original advertising campaign defunction

It is therefore critical to any cross cultural, global or international advertising campaign that a thorough understanding of the target culture is acquired.

Let's examine a few examples of cultural differences in advertising

Even the simplest and most taken for granted aspects of advertising need to be inspected under a cross cultural microscope. Colors, numbers, symbols and images do not all translate well across cultures

Ever Changing Scenarios

The modern global market increasingly turns information into the most critical strategic commodity and communication tool. Advertising is one of the active forms of interaction between the masses and the external environment. It is currently dynamically changing under the influence of trends such as globalization and digitalization. This, in turn, determines a new level of advertising depth and the range of its impact on a potential audience.

As the world and its diversities change, so do human relationships. People's lifestyles are evolving to meet the growing demands of an increasingly mobile-first society. Our understanding of consumer relations has evolved from the relationship between a brand and its customers to those based on one-on-one, Omni channel, immersive, personalized communications.

But how has advertising changed and evolved under the consequences we mentioned above? What in advertising will remain eternal, and what has been reborn into new advertising trends, methods, tools, formulas, or algorithms? And, of course, the most important is how you can implement those into your business and ad practices?

You can find everything you need to know about advertising here: this article will help fill in the gaps in your knowledge from the beginning to the future of advertising. In the course of reading the article, you will discover recent trends in advertising products and will get tips for creating valuable and outstanding advertising time after time.

As a bonus, you will learn how to create effective ads using CGI, which is the key to successful online advertising, increased conversions, and a better customer experience. The marketing department of our product CGI company is happy to be your guide on this adventure.

The advertising industry is constantly evolving, and the past few years have seen some significant changes. There has been a shift towards digital advertising. As more and more people spend time

online, businesses increasingly turn to the internet to reach their target audiences. This has led to

new trends such as programmatic advertising, which uses sophisticated algorithms to target ads to the right people.

We're seeing growth in video advertising. Video is a compelling medium, and it's no surprise that it's becoming increasingly popular with marketers. Thanks to platforms like YouTube and Meta, businesses can reach many people with their video ads.

Social media marketing is becoming more critical than ever. With most people using social media platforms like Meta, Twitter, and Instagram, businesses need to be present on these channels to reach their audiences. Social media marketing allows companies to build relationships with potential and current customers and create a connection with their brand.

With the new digital advertising models, technological progress, and various creative ways to promote a product – let's not delay and dive into recent trends in advertising of products.

CONCLUSION

By way of conclusion, we can see that the principles of advertising run through to cross cultural advertising too. That is - know your market, what is attractive to your target audience and what motivates them. Advertising across cultures is simply about using common sense and analyzing how the different elements of an advertising campaign are impacted by culture and modifying them to best speak to the target audience.

Advertising media has become highly matured one. Owing to the same it has started reading the pulse of the consumer in the perfect manner the appropriate manner in which advertisement media taps customer potential acts as a huge game for business houses. It is up to the business to leverage the efficiency of the advertising agency to their advantage. Prudence lies in allocating the required budget for advertising their products and services through digital media which stands on a higher pedestal than others.

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